

A Study of Stimulating Factors in Self-Motivated Professional Development among Teachers at University Level

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Abstract *The purpose of this study is to find out the factors which stimulate university teachers towards self-motivated professional development at university level. It was a descriptive study based on survey design; a mixed methods design was selected to collect the data through mixed method techniques. 200 questionnaires were distributed with the help of the snowball sampling technique, which helped in reaching 57 teachers for interview. Thematic Analysis, Descriptive Statistics and Chi-Square Test were applied to data. The result shows the intrinsic factors of stimulation were self-thrust towards excellence, respect, acknowledgment and inner satisfaction. On the contrary, extrinsic factors were a good salary package, promotion, better social and professional status and ability to cope with the advanced educational requirements. The study recommends that action through teachers' consideration, reflection and shared vision may include extrinsic and intrinsic factors of motivation.*

Key Words:
CLT, Experimental design, ESL, GMT, Intermediate level learners, Pakistani context.

Introduction

Today professional development for teachers is considered as an obligatory component of educational policies to heighten the overall quality of teaching and learning. As a result, there is an increased demand for research that highlights the features of effective professional development primarily, self-motivated professional development. Around the globe, substantial funds have been allocated to a wide variety of professional development programs through variety of sources but still there is a need to bridge the gap.

Professional development makes teachers resourceful, by helping them improve teaching practices and enhance overall teaching standards. There are different ways to support and encourage teachers to enhance their performance hence; professional development has diverse activities and structures. According to Caffarella and Daffron (2013) the core purpose of professional development is to facilitate a teacher to experience and learn advanced teaching methodologies, extend subject knowledge and stay updated and equipped with advanced educational requirements.

As Gamrat, Zimmerman, Dudek, and Peck (2014) describe, there is always something new teachers can experiment with and acquire to enhance their

teaching learning process, being a teacher demands a continuous professional development and a firm commitment to learn and grow throughout the career progression. According to Geldenhuys and Oosthuizen (2015), today's educational policies and procedures put extra responsibilities on teachers, curriculum makers and on society to be accountable to deliver quality education. As per Hunzicker (2011) in order to meet the higher demands teachers, supposed to get full support through appropriate and effective professional development programs and opportunities.

According to Jogi, Karu, and Krabi (2015) because of its significant role in the education sector no notable development in education sector can be made without effective and supportive professional development. According to Alfred and Nafukho (2010) self-motivated professional development leads towards significant and sustainable progress in overall education change to develop and grow with the capacity to meet teacher's individual needs. According to Altbach, Reisberg, and Rumbley (2009) approaches towards professional development have now become much more demanding and long term. Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations factors of professional development needed to be explored and research to know that what actually causes motivation in teachers in different contexts and situations.

Currently, the area of motivation among teachers has been stressed a lot to investigate, the noticeable factors of motivation which produce and ensure success. Intrinsic motivation is a vital factor especially when considering self-directed professional development. Avalos (2011) considers intrinsic motivation of teachers to consist of the qualities and characteristics of a teacher, focus and motivation to perform an activity with free will, and positive determination for the joy of success. This complements actions without any pressure, burden or external factors or motives. Teachers who own intrinsic motivation are motivated because of the inner satisfaction of attaining proficiency and pleasure of accomplishment to attain next level as well as to full-fill the long-term goals.

On the contrary, according to Borko (2004) extrinsic motivation refers to the inspiration one has to do an activity not for the joy of it, but to accomplish some external goal. According to Burns and Lawrie (2015) teacher who participates in an activity to get praise, money, or a reward as well as avoid being back or out of the pace from an external figure is considered as possessing extrinsic motivation. Extrinsic motivation does have short-term motivational characteristics, according to Buskist, Sikorski, Buckley, and Saville (2002) extrinsic pressures are most often shown in educational context set by the institution and in established standards which meant to be met and achieved.

Objectives and Question of the Study

To find out the factors of stimulation towards self-motivated professional development. Therefore, the study asks: What stimulates (intrinsic/extrinsic) to self-motivated professional development?

Methodology

Research Design

It was a descriptive study based on survey design, based upon the theoretical framework a mixed methods design was selected.

Population

The population of the study was the teachers; who have started their career from bottom line (low grade/ designation level), through self-motivation developed their career, teaching in social sciences departments of public universities of Punjab.

Sample

The researcher has used snowball sampling technique to select the subjects from population by applying snowball sampling technique; data was collected from 57 teachers.

Data Collection

Firstly, researcher has sought permission for data collection and gathered basic information about university faculty to know about the teachers who have promoted from bottom position to current position. After getting written permission and knowing about targeted teachers, the researcher personally visited the universities, administered questionnaires and conducted interviews. Total 57 university teachers were interviewed.

Instruments

For interviews semi-structured interview was developed, interviews were conducted and transcribed by the researcher. Data collected from interviews was coded and analyzed for emergent themes in a similar manner to sequential mixed strategies design. Quantitative data was gathered through questionnaire consisted on close-ended and three scale items, which was administered to 200 teachers from which 57 questionnaires were selected, who were then chosen for in depth interviews for qualitative data. The responses gathered through instruments were examined statistically in order to generate descriptive statistics.

Table 1. Responses of University Teachers about Intrinsic Factors of Motivation

Intrinsic Factors of Motivation	n	%	χ^2	P
			23.351	<001
Inner Satisfaction	30	53		
Feeling to get Recognized & Respected	10	18		
Confronted Nature	9	15		
Meet Friends/Family Aspiration	8	14		

Table 1 shows the responses of university teachers about intrinsic factors of motivation. 30 (53%) respondents stated their main objective towards professional development was inner satisfaction, for 10 (18%) it was to get recognized in professional world, 9 (15%) said they had confronted nature and took their progression as challenge, 8 (14%) respondents want to meet their friends and family aspiration. The results of chi-square, χ^2 (DF=3, N=57) =23.351, $p < .001$ revealed that the major intrinsic factor of professional development was inner satisfaction.

Table 2. Responses of University Teachers about Extrinsic Factors of Motivation

Extrinsic Factors of Motivation	n	%	χ^2	P
			8.474	0.037
Career Progression	23	40		
Financial Raise	15	26		
Social & Professional Status	10	18		
Peer Pressure /Professional Competition	9	16		

Table 2 shows the responses of university teachers about extrinsic factors of motivation. For 23 (40%) respondents career progression was the extrinsic factor of motivation, for 15 (26%) financial raise and for 10 (18%) to get desired social and professional status was the factor and 9 (16%) did it to cope up and meet the peer pressure and professional competition. The results of chi-square, χ^2 (df=3, N=57) = 8.474, p=0.037) revealed for most of the respondents' career progression was the major factor of professional development.

Intrinsic Factors of Motivation

Majority of the participants value inner satisfaction, the feeling of accomplishment given them the joy, they strived towards their goal for personal satisfaction and accomplishment. Some of them said the appreciation and motivation of their seniors, students, family and friends made them motivated. Few of them considered some heart touching moments to be their motivational factor like; the award of being 'best teacher', 'certificate of appreciation' and parents and students comments and praise.

Extrinsic Factors of Motivation

Majority of the participants upgraded their qualifications for their career growth, especially to excel to the senior grades. Few of them wanted to enhance their social and professional status. For some of them financial raise was the reward to grow more. Some of them said the reputation, respect and recognition kept them motivated and some said their ideal were their inspiration and motivation they always wanted to be like them so they work hard and followed them to be like them one day.

Results

The following findings have been made on the basis of data analysis.

Intrinsic Factors

The intrinsic factors which stimulate teachers towards self-motivated professional development.

- Inner satisfaction teachers valued their self-thirst and self-satisfaction to get perfection, by reaching to the end goal.
- The aim to reach to their desired goal and meet their dream, to achieve sense of achievement.
- The admiration and appreciation from their seniors and students.
- The emotional, heart touching moments, like; the award of 'best teacher', 'certificate of appreciation', students' gratitude and compliments.
- The praise and encouragement of friends, family and colleagues.

- To meet friends, family and seniors' expectations and to pay back their confidence and encouragement.

Extrinsic Factors

The extrinsic factors which stimulate teachers towards self-motivated professional development were.

- Career growth; particularly to excel to senior grades through promotion.
- Better social and professional status, position and empowerment.
- To get respect, good reputation, admiration and recognition in society.
- To have financial raise for better living style.

The major extrinsic factor of motivation amongst teachers was career growth; particularly, excel to senior grades and get promotion. Some of them were desired to enhance their social and professional status and position. Few of them want to get good repute; respect and recognition in society and financial raise. Almost all teachers reported one of the most important factors of motivation was to meet their family and friends' expectations and support.

On the contrary, majority of the teachers reported the biggest intrinsic factor of their intrinsic motivation was inner satisfaction they really valued their self-thirst and self-satisfaction. For some of them the feeling to reach to their desired goal and meet their dream and to get the sense of achievement was the stimulation. For some of them the respect and appreciation from their seniors and students were the instigator. Some of them considered certain heart touching moments to be their reasons of motivation like; the award of 'best teacher', 'certificate of appreciation', students' gratitude and compliments.

Discussion

McLoughlin and Lee (2008) there are so many studies which addressed the need and effect of professional development but still factors which stimulate self-motivated professional development need to be explored more. The present study aimed to get an insight into extrinsic and intrinsic factors of stimulations which drive self-motivated professional development.

Regarding the rapid changes in advanced educational contexts, Mills (2011) discussed that professionally developed teachers are supposed to meet the shifting prospects of stakeholders. Further supported by National Comprehensive Center for Teacher Quality (2012) teachers need to update themselves with new technologies and endorse advanced administrative and researcher roles to be with pace. According to Gulamhussein (2013) though recent educational changes are well acknowledged in the literature, yet researchers provided less definite results on how to support teachers' self-motivation process.

According to Ng (2015) self-motivated professional development can increase teachers' effectiveness more extensively and less expensively yet more relevantly. As a result, there is a growing need to support self-motivated professional development in the hope to get advanced and effective educational services. Connell (2012) discussed that external and internal factors of professional development improvement are powerful enough, specific enough, and sustain able enough to alter the culture of education.

As described by Steinert (2010) self-motivation is a process which stimulate individuals to take initiative, identify their needs, set goals, finds resources, implement

strategies and be consistent towards their goal. Findings support these views, that teachers self-motivation have made them grow, they have started their career from very low grade has become university teachers. They took a charge of their development, identified their needs and made ways to reach to their goal.

As stated by Sun, Penuel, Frank, Gallagher, and Youngs (2013) there are many approaches to help teachers develop, but the time is to put more stress to motivate teachers to value their competence in order to enhance self-confidence and self-motivation. Outcomes of the study match with these views and provide evidence that for professional development teachers do not require policies and programs they just need to take charge of their development find out the opportunities to grow. Following outcomes further aligned with Wang, Y.W.et al. (2003) self-motivation and determination should be the ultimate goal of education it should impart various skills that empower individuals to drive their learning.

According to Wright (2009) self-thrust and inner satisfaction provides the support and strength to grow because the success of professional development depends on realization that it is needed and responsibility to own the chosen profession by heart. Findings of the study incorporate with this opinion for majority of the teachers the intrinsic factor of their motivation was inner satisfaction. They valued their self-thirst and self-satisfaction to be expert and professional in their field and the feeling to reach to their desired goal and to fulfill their dream.

According to Yoon, Duncan, Lee, Scarloff, and Shapley (2007) to enhance learning outcomes in international context, it is important to understand the challenges faced by teachers and to provide them the appreciation and respect which keep them motivated. The findings of the study support these opinions that teachers really appreciated the respect and appreciation they got from their seniors, students friends and family, their confidence and encouragement kept them stimulated.

According to Hulme (2012) the most effective ways to reach the professional development opportunities is provide the teachers the position and status which they deserve and look for. As evidence the present study provides the facts that the teachers get motivated for their career growth; particularly to excel to senior grades for promotion. Some of them were desired to enhance their social and professional status and position. Few of them were roused for good repute; respect and recognition in society.

Recommendations

Keeping in view the findings and conclusion, the following suggestions have been made.

- Teaching profession should get the respect and ownership it deserves to attract the top brains to be a part of it.
- Professional development policies, plans and programs need to be aligned with teachers' actual needs and advance requirements.
- The best possible infrastructure should be provided to teachers for smooth development.
- Self-motivated professional development should be encouraged and important measures should be taken to support the environment which ensures motivation.
- Further research in this area should be done to cover up the deficiencies.

References

- Alfred, M. V., & Nafukho, F. M. (2010). *International and comparative adult and continuing education*. In C. E. Kasworm, A. D. Rose, & J. M. Ross-Gordon (Eds.), *Handbook of adult and continuing education* (pp. 93–102). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Altbach, P. G., Reisberg, L., & Rumbley, L. E. (2009). *Trends in global higher education: Tracking an academic revolution*. Retrieved from the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.
- Avalos, B. (2011). *Teacher professional development in teaching and teacher education over ten years*. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 27(1), 10–20.
<http://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2010.08.007>
- Borko, H. (2004). *Professional development and teacher learning: Mapping the terrain*. *Educational Researcher*, 33(8), 3–15. Retrieved from <http://edr.sagepub.com/content/33/8/3.short>
- Burns, M., & Lawrie, J. (2015). Where it's needed most: *Quality Professional Development for all Teachers*. Retrieved from Inter-Agency Network for Education in Emergencies (INEE) website: <http://www.ineesite.org/en/>
- Buskist, W., Sikorski, J., Buckley, T., & Saville, B. K. (2002). *Elements of Master Teaching*. In S. F. Davis & W. Buskist (Eds.), *The teaching of psychology: Essays in honor of Wilbert J. McKeachie and Charles L. Brewer* (pp. 27–39). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Caffarella, R. S., & Daffron, S. R. (2013). *Planning Programs for Adult Learners: A Practical Guide* (3rd ed.). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Gamrat, C., Zimmerman, H. T., Dudek, J., & Peck, K. (2014). *Personalized Workplace Learning: An Exploratory Study on Digital Badging within a Teacher Professional Development Program*. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 45(6), 1136–1148. <http://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12200>
- Geldenuys, J. L., & Oosthuizen, L. C. (2015). *Challenges Influencing Teachers' Involvement in Continuous Professional Development: A South African perspective*. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 51, 203–212.
<http://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2015.06.010>
- Gulamhussein, A. (2013). *Teaching the Teachers: Effective professional development in an Era of High Stakes Accountability*. Retrieved from Center for Public Education website: <http://www.centerforpubliceducation.org/teachingtheteachers>
- Hunzicker, J. (2011). *Effective Professional Development for Teachers: A Checklist*. *Professional Development in Education*, 37(2), 177–179.
<http://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2010.523955>

- Jögi, L., Karu, K., & Krabi, K. (2015). *Rethinking Teaching and Teaching Practice at University in a Lifelong Learning Context*. *International Review of Education*, 61(1), 61–77. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s11159-015-9467-z>
- Kukulska-Hulme, A. (2012). *How Should the Higher Education Workforce Adapt to Advancements in Technology for Teaching and Learning? Internet and Higher Education*, 15(4), 247–254. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2011.12.002>
- McLoughlin, C., & Lee, M. J. (2008). *The Three P's of Pedagogy for the Networked Society: Personalization, Participation, and Productivity*. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 20(1), 10–27. Retrieved from <http://www.isetl.org/ijtlhe/>
- Mills, G. E. (2011). *Action Research: A Guide for the Teacher Researcher*. (4th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson.
- National Comprehensive Center for Teacher Quality. (2012). *Linking Teacher Evaluation to Professional Development: Focusing on Improving Teaching and Learning* (Research & Policy Brief). Washington, DC: Goe, L., Biggers, K., Croft, A.
- Ng, W. (2015). Adopting New Digital Technologies in Education: *Professional learning*. In W. Ng (Ed.), *New Digital Technology in Education: Conceptualizing Professional Learning for Educators* (pp. 25–48). New York, NY: Springer.
- O'Connell, K. (2012). *Professional Faculty Development for Teaching Online Courses at a Proprietary University* (Doctoral Dissertation). Retrieved from Pro Quest Dissertations & Theses Full Text database. (UMI No. 3548787)
- Steinert, Y. (2010). *Faculty Development: from Workshops to Communities of Practice* (AMEE Guide no. 33). *Medical Teacher*, 32(5), 425–428. <http://doi.org/10.3109/01421591003677897>
- Sun, M., Penuel, W. R., Frank, K. A., Gallagher, H. A., & Youngs, P. (2013). *Shaping Professional Development to Promote the Diffusion of Instructional Expertise among Teachers*. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 35(3), 344–369. <http://doi.org/10.3102/0162373713482763>
- Wang, Y.-W., Davidson, M. M., Yakushko, O. F., Savoy, H. B., Tan, J. A., & Bleier, J. K. (2003). *The Scale of Ethno Cultural Empathy: Development, Validation, and Reliability*. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 50(2), 221. <http://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0167.50.2.221>
- Webster-Wright, A. (2009). *Reframing Professional Development Through Understanding Authentic Professional Learning*. *Review of Educational Research*, 79(2), 702–739. <http://doi.org/10.3102/0034654308330970>
- Yoon, K. S., Duncan, T., Lee, S. W.-Y., Scarloss, B., & Shapley, K. L. (2007). *Reviewing the Evidence on how Teacher Professional Development Affects Student Achievement*. (Issues & Answers Report, REL 2007–No. 033). Retrieved from the U.S. Department of Education, Institute of Education Sciences website: <http://ies.ed.gov/ncee/edlabs>